

AusTraits: A national database on the traits of Australia's complete flora

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM
PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP720
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - June 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	UNSW
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	<p>Western Sydney University Royal Botanic Gardens and Domain Trust Macquarie University Centre for Australian National Biodiversity Research The University of Melbourne EcoCommons CSIRO Landcare Research New Zealand University of New England Murdoch University Department of Agriculture, Water and the Environment: Australian Biological Resources Study Parks Australia Atlas of Living Australia Arthur Rylah Institute for Environmental Research NSW Department of Planning, Industry and Environment Western Australia Department of Biodiversity, Conservation and Attractions Greening Australia University of Arizona</p>
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Daniel Falster

1.1 Background

AusTraits is a curated open-source database that integrates and harmonises plant trait data for Australian plant taxa. Trait data are used for myriad research and conservation agendas, including understanding plant responses to bushfires, how species change across climatic gradients, and the distribution and evolution of key traits across taxonomic groups. Trait-based research agendas across

the world are accelerated by the existence of easily accessible, accurate, tabular trait compilations. Yet prior to AusTraits no broad-scale trait compilation existed for Australian plant taxa; global compilations generally include only sparse data coverage for Australian plant taxa.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

Our core project aim was to develop the AusTraits plant trait database into a National Data Asset with coverage for as many Australian taxa and as many traits as possible, merging together data from disparate sources. Auxiliary aims were to: 1) create a database that was underpinned by a carefully considered, well-documented database structure; 2) create an open, transparent, and reusable workflow that harmonises diverse sources into the desired database structure; 3) ensure all data were mapped to explicitly defined trait concepts and, for categorical traits, allowable trait values; and 4) publish the trait dictionary as a standalone output.

Toward building a bigger trait database with increased taxonomic, geographic, and trait coverage, we have added 92 datasets to AusTraits using funds from this ARDC project, with another 30 datasets to be added over the coming month. This has nearly doubled the number of trait values in AusTraits. These represent a selection of field-collected datasets, data extracted from taxonomic descriptions, and experimental datasets. Not only did the number of values in AusTraits increase dramatically, but we also now have near-complete coverage for three key traits, plant growth form, woodiness, and life history, across Australia's flora.

Enhancements to our database structure now allow us to better document the metadata associated with each data value, including mapping in `entity type` (individual, population or species); context properties (e.g. fire severity; leaf temperature); and details about location, method, and taxonomy. The fields (columns) within our database are now aligned to published standards whenever possible.

An expanded, formally published trait dictionary has just been released as the AusTraits Plant Dictionary (APD), registered with a domain on w3id.org and available through Research Vocabularies Australia. The 509 trait concepts included in this dictionary have been developed by the AusTraits team, in consultation with experts, including through three series of workshops. In addition to defining precise, explicit trait concepts and well-defined lists of allowable trait values, each trait concept now includes all best-practice metadata, including lists of references, links to identical/similar/related traits in other databases, reviewers, and keywords. The dictionary has been transformed into both a formal rdf vocabulary and "human friendly" outputs, to allow the definitions to be broadly reused.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

Figure 1. An overview of AusTraits achievements

The above figures document trait coverage for AusTraits version 2.1.0 (at the start of the grant period) and AusTraits version 5.0 (to be released in June 2023). Each plot is a grid of taxon names (species level taxa only) versus traits, numbered sequentially based on coverage). A cell is coloured yellow if data exist for that trait by taxon combination in AusTraits. Note the different y-scales, as total species coverage has increased, with some traits now having near-complete coverage. Notice as well, the strong increase in “moderate coverage” for traits ranked between 30-100, which previously has much more limited data. These are predominately the traits added through the flora-scraping and eFLOWER endeavours, although also reflect our ongoing efforts to add data from field experiments that document water relations traits and tissue nutrient contents.

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
Work Package 1: Establish governance arrangements		
1.1 Establish governance arrangements: Confer with key organisations & stakeholders	Governance documents written and reviewed by the AusTraits team.	30/09/2021
1.2 Establish governance arrangements: Approval & publication of proposed governance structure	Governance documents agreed upon by the AusTraits Advisory Board.	29/11/2021
1.3 Yearly governance review	Final meeting of the AusTraits Advisory Board occurred on 29 May 2023.	29/05/2023
Work Package 2: Formalise vocabularies for traits		
2.1.1 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Establish technical ability to have hierarchical traits	The rdf representation of the AusTraits Plant Dictionary (APD) includes a trait hierarchy. This was accomplished by creating a standalone hierarchy and mapping each trait into the appropriate location in the hierarchy, using skos 'broader' and 'narrower' terminology.	30/04/2023
2.1.2 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Establish workflow for publishing vocabularies	We established a preliminary workflow for publishing vocabularies in January 2023, but have since revised our protocol and now have an easy-to-update protocol which uses an R script to merge together all metadata about each trait definition into a triples format, then converts this into rdf representations. These are hosted on our github repository (github.com/traitecoevo/APD) and RVA.	31/05/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
2.2.1 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Plan and hold workshop to establish vocabularies and standards for seed & dispersal traits	We held a 5-session, online workshop to review and refine 30 trait concepts related to seed and dispersal traits.	18/11/2021
2.2.2 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Publish formal vocabularies for seed & dispersal traits	The refined trait concepts and accompanying trait definitions related to seed and dispersal traits were merged into AusTraits, to support better mapping of trait data within the database. These same trait concepts have more recently been incorporated into the AusTraits Plant Dictionary, the APD.	27/11/2022
2.3.1 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Plan and hold workshop to establish vocabularies and standards for leaf & vegetative traits	We held a 5-session online workshop to review and refine 30 trait concepts related to leaf and whole plant vegetative traits.	27/11/2022
2.3.2 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Publish formal vocabularies for leaf & vegetative traits	The refined trait concepts and accompanying trait definitions related to leaf and whole plant vegetative traits were merged into AusTraits, to support better mapping of trait data within the database. These same trait concepts have more recently been incorporated into the AusTraits Plant Dictionary, the APD.	27/11/2022
2.4.1 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Plan and	We held a half day in person workshop to review and refine 35 trait concepts related to floral traits. This was followed up by a	19/05/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
hold workshop to establish vocabularies and standards for floral traits	series of one-on-one discussions about additional traits to score and edits required to existing traits.	
2.4.2 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Publish formal vocabularies for floral traits	The additional trait concepts and accompanying trait definitions related to floral traits were merged into AusTraits and incorporated into the AusTraits Plant Dictionary, the APD. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023
2.5.1 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Plan and hold workshop to establish vocabularies and standards for Minimum Trait Set	As a team we chose to replace this workshop with seeking expert reviews for 70 physiological traits. For each trait we sought out two senior researchers in the field and asked them to review the trait name, trait description, and accompanying trait references. We decided this would have a greater impact on publishing a robust Trait Dictionary, as it ensured all physiological trait concepts would be reviewed. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023
2.5.2 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Publish formal vocabularies for Minimum Trait Set	As a team we chose to replace this workshop with seeking expert reviews for 70 physiological traits. For each trait we sought out two senior researchers in the field and asked them to review the trait name, trait description, and accompanying trait references. We decided this would have a greater impact on publishing a robust Trait Dictionary, as it ensured all physiological trait concepts would be reviewed. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023
2.6.1 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Plan and hold workshop to converge on a	We held a 4-session online workshop to review and refine 30 trait concepts related to fire response and regeneration traits. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
set of fire response traits		
2.6.2 Formalise vocabularies for traits: Publish formal vocabularies for fire response traits	The refined trait concepts and accompanying trait definitions related to fire and regeneration traits were merged into AusTraits, to support better mapping of trait data within the database. These same trait concepts have more recently been incorporated into the AusTraits Plant Dictionary, the APD. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023
Work Package 3: Create AusTraits API		
3.0 Survey currently available trait portals and APIs	The AusTraits team investigated several hosting services for the API including AWS and Zenodo, before making the final decision to build it using the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud Openstack API software. These decisions were carried out in consultation with the Research Technology group (ResTech) at UNSW, who would construct the framework for the API, while AusTraits team would build the code to format the data for sending via the API.	20/12/2021
3.1 Online workshop to scope requirements for accessing AusTraits via API	The AusTraits team held a series of meetings with teams from project partners Atlas of Living Australia, Ecommons and Flora of Australia in which topics such as how the data would be displayed, what kinds of trait data and the most appropriate API endpoints (how best to “package” the data) for each platform were discussed and decided.	28/02/2022
3.2 Create a verified API for AusTraits, for accessing AusTraits from biodiversity portals	Working closely with UNSW ResTech, we delivered an API hosted on the Nectar cloud servers with bespoke API endpoints for easy display on the ALA (currently live) and Ecommons (still under construction) websites. The ALA endpoints include a way to download any AusTraits data available for taxa in their species factsheets via a made-for-purpose “traits tab”, accompanied by information about how to access the full database and interpret the data. For an example, see	31/01/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
	https://bie.ala.org.au/species/https://id.biodiversity.org.au/node/apni/2887077#ausTraits	
Work Package 4: Identify & import legacy data		
4.1.1 Identify taxa, locations and traits with low coverage (write scripts and test repeatedly)	Team members repeatedly summarise AusTraits trait data by traits, taxa, and locations to determine locations with lowest coverage and focus our efforts on sourcing data sets to fill these gaps.	30/04/2023
4.1.2 Identify legacy data that are good sources to enhance coverage	Team members repeatedly search Google Scholar and the reference section of manuscripts to identify datasets to incorporate into AusTraits.	30/06/2023
4.2.1 Access, digitise & import legacy data directly into AusTraits	Copies of the manuscripts identified in work package 4.1.2 are downloaded into a shared folder, and data are transcribed for inclusion into AusTraits. For datasets collected by researchers who are still active in the field, we contact the contributor directly to try and source the raw data files, while for other datasets we simply transcribe data available in the publication. During this project we will have imported 92 new data sources and nearly doubled the number of trait values within AusTraits. <i>(Most recent additions are on the austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release. There are expected to be an additional 30 datasets added over the coming month.)</i>	30/06/2023
4.3.1 Access, digitise & import legacy data into eFLOWER (ongoing)	We increased the coverage of floral trait data by scoring 35 individual traits for 1976 plant species. Taxa scored were those selected by the Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP) project and representing ~95% of all known plant genera in Australia. In total 28,744 floral trait values were scored.	30/01/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
4.3.2 Merge current eFLOWER data into AusTraits (repeated every 6-12 months)	The above-mentioned 28,744 floral trait values were merged into AusTraits. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	25/05/2023
4.4.1 Access, digitise & import legacy data into Minimum Trait Set	Although creating an official list of traits to include in the Minimum Trait Set was not completed, we focused on incorporating data from a draft list of MTS traits for which data existed in taxonomic descriptions. Data on 36 traits were scraped from Australia's national and state floras, with 570,000 trait values added to AusTraits. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023
4.4.2 Add Minimum Trait Set traits to AusTraits and map any preexisting data onto these traits	Data on 36 traits were scraped from Australia's national and state floras, with 570,000 trait values added to AusTraits. <i>(On austraits.build develop branch and will be part of 30/06/2023 AusTraits release)</i>	31/05/2023
Work Package 5: Expand data coverage		
5.1 Expand AusTraits data coverage through collections in active, aligned research grants and second open call for new data	We have been actively interacting with researchers across Australia throughout the grant, building relationships and soliciting data. Our second open call for data was initiated in November 2022, when all members of the AusTraits team attended the Ecological Society of Australia meeting in Wollongong, where we staffed a dedicated AusTraits table for a week. In February 2023, we began emailing researchers across Australia requesting recently collected (and legacy) datasets for inclusion into AusTraits. This work package will be ongoing until 30/06/2023, with data included in the 30/06/2023 AusTraits release.	30/06/2023
Work Package 6: Trait imputation		

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
6.1 Identify traits where imputation (gap filling) is most feasible & beneficial	This has been an ongoing effort over the past year, involving both AusTraits staff and AusTraits partners at Western Sydney University. A half day workshop on 22 May 2023 finalised the list of traits where imputation is most feasible, considering the total taxon and spatial coverage for each trait in AusTraits at this time.	31/05/2023
6.2 Create imputation workflow and script, to run iteratively over time for specific traits	<p>We took advantage of existing scripts to test imputation workflows and compare the accuracy of imputed trait values for specific traits. We then refined the workflow to more accurately impute trait values for the traits we had identified under work package 6.1. The workflow used is documented in a vignette on our GitHub repository github.com/traitecoevo/austraits.build, allowing others to impute data using this workflow. The script and a dataset using the current AusTraits data to input trait values for all native taxa in Australia for 6 traits will be deposited in the Zenodo repository in the coming months. This dataset can be reused by researchers or regenerated from the most recent AusTraits data using the accompanying script.</p> <p>In addition to the core AusTraits team and partners, we involved 2 undergraduate computer science students at Western Sydney University, who developed an alternative imputation workflow for AusTraits data. This method is being prepared for publication in a scientific journal.</p>	30/06/2023
Work Package 7: Database usability and improvement		
7.1 Database usability and improvement: Design R package that includes basic functions to query AusTraits	With additional funding from UNSW, the `austraits` R package (https://traitecoevo.github.io/austraits/) was developed, allowing users to access, explore and wrangle data from the AusTraits database in R. In November 2022, this package won the inaugural ARDC Award for New Software Developer (Dr Fonti Kar).	30/09/2021

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
7.2 Database usability and improvement: Provide AusTraits data for testing in designated use cases	Researchers in several research groups have been working with AusTraits data to identify required changes to the database structure and possible sources of error or ambiguity.	30/06/2023
7.3 Database usability and improvement: Seek feedback and identify improvements from use case leaders and other researchers	Following on from work package 7.2, researchers have provided feedback on required changes to the database structure and possible sources of error or ambiguity. Their responses informed many of the database structure changes we made in 2022, including 1) allowing replicate counts to be mapped in at the observation level (rather than the trait level); 2) consolidating two “date” entries into a single field; 3) separating data measured on different entities (individuals, population, or species) into separate observations. Their responses also alerted us to possible errors in trait data, usually derived from trait concepts being insufficiently precise or insufficiently documented. This feedback helped inform trait concept revisions made during workshops and internal reviews.	30/06/2023
Work Package 8: Data use and access		
8.1 Data use and access: Provide access of data via biodiversity platform (Atlas of Living Australia)	The Atlas of Living Australia has incorporated a `traits tab` that displays AusTraits trait value summaries and included links to download the raw data (for a given taxon) and the accompanying trait definitions. The species tabs are visited approximately 2000 times a day. For instance, see https://bie.ala.org.au/species/https://id.biodiversity.org.au/taxon/apni/51293610#ausTraits	28/02/2023
8.2 Data use and access: Provide access of data via biodiversity platform	EcoCommons has completed significant work toward integrating AusTraits data into their platform and are likely to have integrated some AusTraits data in the coming months. They worked up a use case using AusTraits data to	28/02/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
(EcoCommons)	demonstrate how AusTraits data can be used in their models: https://www.ecocommons.org.au/austraits-use-case/	
8.3 Data use and access: Provide access of data via biodiversity platform (Flora of Australia)	The Flora of Australia is currently working to relaunch their platform and will resume deliberations about how best to display AusTraits data once this is complete.	
8.4 Data use and access: Provide access of data via biodiversity platform (BIEN)	BIEN is currently working to relaunch their platform and will resume deliberations about how best to display AusTraits data once this is complete.	
Work Package 9: AusTraits moving forward		
9.1 AusTraits, moving forward: In-person meeting with AusTraits team to discuss accomplishments , breakout groups to summarise progress on work packages.	The core AusTraits team have had several meetings to discuss strategies for ongoing management of the database. This includes nascent planning for future funding calls, possible strategies for maintaining the functionality of AusTraits in the absence of funding, and new partnerships which may allow for the database to grow (e.g. expansion to other taxa, or more specific aspects of plant science).	31/05/2023
Work Package 10: Impact/Outcome Monitoring Systems (Implementation Work Package)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tracking of the download of datasets using the Counter Code of Practice for Research Data in Repositories 		

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated ongoing communications with end-users regarding their usage 		
10.1 Construct COUNTER-compliant API for AusTraits	The API we constructed to deliver data to data portals is counter compliant and able to document the number of data requests it receives.	31/01/2023
10.2 Optional user registration (via project website) and survey	Since most users access AusTraits data through Zenodo, the austraits R package, or the ALA traits tab, there is not a common site to which we could direct AusTraits users to register or complete a survey. However, we have recently decided that at future talks we will ask the audience to partake in a live survey asking them if they were aware of AusTraits prior to the talk, if they have used the AusTraits database, and in what sector they are employed.	31/08/2023

2.2 Project outputs

- AusTraits database:** The first public version of the AusTraits database was released on 14 July 2021 on Zenodo (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568417), with 2 subsequent releases and another release planned for 30 June 2023. This database now includes more than 1.75 million individual trait values, across more than 500 traits and nearly every one of Australia's nearly 30,000 plant taxa. This database has already supported many research projects, and the accompanying data paper (see below) is cited about once every 10 days (https://scholar.google.com.au/scholar?cites=13955903476754965983&as_sdt=2005&scioldt=0,5&hl=en).
- AusTraits data paper:** A data paper on AusTraits was published in Scientific Data in September 2021 (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-021-01006-6>). This data paper is readily findable, open-source, and provides researchers with no prior connection to AusTraits an introduction to the project and information about how to source and reuse the data.
- Austraits R package:** The austraits R package (<https://traitecoevo.github.io/austraits/>) offers a series of R functions that allow users to access, explore and wrangle data from the AusTraits

database. In November 2022, this package won the inaugural ARDC Award for New Software Developer.

4. **Austraits.build workflow:** The R code that integrates and harmonises the individual datasets into AusTraits has been reformatted into a standalone workflow that other researchers can use to build their own trait databases that are fully interoperable with AusTraits. This code will shortly be released as a standalone R package, `traits.build`. Currently, another ARDC-funded group (<https://doi.org/10.47486/DC011>), InverTraits (<https://invertebratesaustralia.org/invertraits>), is successfully using the AusTraits workflow to build their database of invertebrate traits, allowing them to efficiently build a trait database that is already underpinned by an established database structure.
5. **AusTraits Plant Dictionary:** The pipeline that creates the AusTraits database requires the existence of a trait dictionary where all accepted trait concepts are explicitly defined and described. Each numeric trait must include an allowable range and standard units, while each categorical trait must include a list of allowable values. The original trait dictionary has been expanded and rebranded as the AusTraits Plant Dictionary (APD), a formally published vocabulary. It includes additional metadata fields (references, keywords, reviewers, links to other trait databases) and is output in both human friendly (.docx, .pdf) and machine readable (.ttl) formats. The machine-readable formats are hosted on Research Vocabularies Australia, with the APD schema registered at w3id (<https://w3id.org/APD>). The definitions can now easily be reused by other trait databases worldwide and the meaning of individual trait measurements in AusTraits is better documented. A data paper describing the data dictionary will be submitted to the journal *Scientific Data* by mid-June.
6. **AusTraits API:** We constructed an API hosted on the Nectar cloud servers with bespoke API endpoints for easy display of AusTraits data on various biodiversity platforms (<https://github.com/traitecoevo/austraits-api>). The endpoints from this API are being used by the Atlas of Living Australia to display AusTraits taxon-specific traits summaries on a custom-made traits tab (e.g. <https://bie.ala.org.au/species/https://id.biodiversity.org.au/node/apni/2912814#ausTraits>). These traits tabs are visited approximately 2000 times per day.
7. **Taxon matching algorithm for Australian taxa:** An important component of the AusTraits workflow is harmonising taxonomic names, such that the same taxon concept has the same name for all data entries in AusTraits. This requires scripts that both catch minor typos and align outdated names with their current name (synonymous terms). This workflow has been shared across many research groups and will shortly be repackaged as a standalone R package AusFlora.

8. **Tabular data from floras:** One of our largest data sources has been extracting morphological trait values from Australia's state and national floras for 36 key traits, with a total of more than 570,000 trait values added to AusTraits from this initiative. This has included developing a novel text-matching workflow that has been written up in a manuscript that will shortly be submitted to the journal *Ecoinformatics*. In addition, we manually gap-filled data for three key traits, plant growth form, life history, and woodiness, achieving near-complete coverage for Australia's flora. The existence of these data is being written up as a separate submission to the *Australian Journal of Botany*.
9. **Research papers:** We have actively promoted the use of AusTraits in our research programs and there have been a growing number of research outputs from our labs that use AusTraits data. A sampling is:
- Adeleye, M. A., Haberle, S. G., Gallagher, R., Andrew, S. C., & Herbert, A. (2023). Changing plant functional diversity over the last 12,000 years provides perspectives for tracking future changes in vegetation communities. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1-12.
 - Stephens, R. E., Gallagher, R., Dun, L., Cornwell, W., & Sauquet, H. (2023). Insects pollinated flowering plants for most of angiosperm evolutionary history. *New Phytologist* (in press)
 - Gallagher, R. V., Allen, S. P., Mackenzie, B. D., Keith, D. A., Nolan, R. H., Rumpff, L., ... & Auld, T. D. (2022). An integrated approach to assessing abiotic and biotic threats to post-fire plant species recovery: Lessons from the 2019–2020 Australian fire season. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 31(10), 2056-2069.
 - Gallagher, R. V., Allen, S., Mackenzie, B. D., Yates, C. J., Gosper, C. R., Keith, D. A., ... & Auld, T. D. (2021). High fire frequency and the impact of the 2019–2020 megafires on Australian plant diversity. *Diversity and Distributions*, 27(7), 1166-1179.
 - Stephens, R. E., Sauquet, H., Guerin, G. R., Jiang, M., Falster, D., & Gallagher, R. V. (2022). Climate shapes community flowering periods across biomes. *Journal of Biogeography*, 49(7), 1205-1218.
 - Andrew, S. C., Gallagher, R. V., Wright, I. J., & Mokany, K. (2022). Assessing the vulnerability of plant functional trait strategies to climate change. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 31(6), 1194-1206.
 - Guerin, G. R., Gallagher, R. V., Wright, I. J., Andrew, S. C., Falster, D. S., Wenk, E., ... & Sparrow, B. (2022). Environmental associations of abundance-weighted functional traits in Australian plant communities. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 58, 98-109.
 - Andrew, S. C., Mokany, K., Falster, D. S., Wenk, E., Wright, I. J., Merow, C., ... & Gallagher, R. V. (2021). Functional diversity of the Australian flora: strong links to species richness and climate. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 32(2), e13018.

10. Encoding database metadata: Initially our database metadata was available only through Zenodo and the only metadata that could be included was that which Zenodo supported. In addition, through conversations with our ARDC liaison, we learned that the Zenodo metadata could not be automatically uploaded to RDA, UNSWorks, or other data discovery portals. Although we could not influence changes to the larger bioinformatics platforms we have been involved in several innovative and ongoing projects to better document database metadata and have it shared with data discovery portals. First, we elected to code the project metadata directly into the distributed database, mapping in all the FAIR data requirements. Second, we now have an ongoing relationship with bioinformaticians at the UNSW Library to develop a system to harvest these encoded metadata directly into Zenodo, and then onward to UNSWorks. They are using AusTraits as a test case for a new system they are developing. If successful it will be available to other users of our database structure.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

Our extensive outreach and training activities are described under other report sections below.

Outreach activities: Please see answers under section 5 below, as all conference presentations fit under both categories. We have not documented the number of people who attended each talk.

Training activities: The vignettes written (see section 5) and the development of the austraits R package.

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

From the outset, we have considered sustainability into the design of AusTraits. As funding for data assets is difficult to secure, AusTraits has been developed in a way that allows for breaks in funding. In particular, the database is assembled using open source tools, and is archived on Zenodo, which means that the data are forever available. The only maintenance cost is the cost of running the API delivering data into the ALA.

A second decision we made was to build general tools that would enable other groups to also build a trait database and vocabulary. This allows us to partner with them, and thereby expand the range of funding sources.

We have also dedicated significant time in the ARDC funding period to building the national reputation of AusTraits in the research community and with environmental agencies to ensure the database has

‘champions’ which promote its value and utility. This extends to international efforts to promote the database (and the ARDC funding of database management, a rare undertaking globally) via the Open Traits Network (<https://opentraits.org/>). For instance, AusTraits featured prominently in the 2022 Open Traits Network Virtual Meeting, where the build workflow was showcased.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	Data archive: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568417 (persistent project link, with additional doi's for each release) Data paper: https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01006-6
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Dataset metadata record for data asset is in Zenodo with type 'Dataset' at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568417 (this doi is used to cite all versions and resolves to latest version metadata in Zenodo)
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	Dataset in RDA: https://researchdata.edu.au/austraits-curated-plant-australian-flora/1957052
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they exist)	N/A
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	Dataset DOI is in Zenodo metadata record at: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568417
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	The dataset is freely available on Zenodo under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence
7	All data outputs are made	The data can be downloaded from the Zenodo repository

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
	available through a repository	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568417
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	AusTraits API endpoints allow data to be sourced by other biodiversity platforms. (https://github.com/traitecoevo/austraits-api)
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	N/A
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	The DOI points to a Zenodo landing page. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568417
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	N/A
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	Since the data are released through Zenodo, the project landing page will persist forever.
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	A large component of the most recent AusTraits release was adjusting the database structure and the fields within AusTraits to align with published standards, including DarwinCore, ETS, and Oboe. A beta version of our machine readable ontology is available on the austraits.build GitHub repository.
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	The most recent AusTraits release includes an additional table that summarises all project metadata using DataCite elements.

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	See 13 & 14 above.
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	On our Zenodo release we have included linked ORCIDs for all researchers, the two ARDC GrantID (https://doi.org/10.47486/DP720) and other grants received
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	The dataset is freely available on Zenodo under a <u>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International</u> licence
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	Licence indicated on https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5112001 and is machine-readable
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	The Zenodo landing page contains a preferred citation
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	The Zenodo landing page includes a link to the full project repository at https://github.com/traitecoevo/austraits.build/tree/v3.0.2 . This page includes all the original data and metadata merged into AusTraits as well as the code used to compile the database. All functions used to compile AusTraits are documented, and project-level vignettes describe the exact meaning of each element within the database.
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	All metadata associated with each dataset incorporated into AusTraits are included as elements within the database structure. Each element is clearly defined within the database's definition tables.

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
Created AusTraits website	Created a project website that summarises project goals, current work packages, team members, project partners, and project impact.	https://austraits.org/
Published data paper in Scientific Data	Falster, D., Gallagher, R., Wenk, E.H. <i>et al.</i> AusTraits, a curated plant trait database for the Australian flora. <i>Sci Data</i> 8 , 254 (2021).	https://doi-org.wwwproxy1.library.unsw.edu.au/10.1038/s41597-021-01006-6
Wrote vignettes introducing AusTraits and the austraits.build workflow	On the project GitHub repository, we offer a series of vignettes that summarise the austraits database structure, how to submit data, how to add data, and a copy of the AusTraits dictionary (prior to it becoming the APD).	http://traitecoevo.github.io/austraits.build/
Featured in ARDC news story, Plant Trait Data Guides Australia's Bushfire Recovery	The use of AusTraits data in informing bushfire recovery management decisions was highlighted in an ARDC news story.	https://ardc.edu.au/article/plant-trait-data-guides-australias-bushfire-recovery/
Featured in ARDC news story, Shaping Research Software: An Interview With Fonti Kar	UNSW staff Fonti Kar won the Ecological Society of Australia's inaugural "ARDC Award for New Developers of Open Source Software in Ecology". This article profiles her work.	https://ardc.edu.au/article/shaping-research-software-an-interview-with-fonti-kar/

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
Featured in ARDC Impact Booklet, <i>Partnering for Success</i>	AusTraits will be featured as a case study in the June 2023 ARDC Annual Impact Report: "Impact Case Study for Earth and Environmental Research"	
Featured in ARDC-funded press release about the integration of AusTraits with the global TRY database	Science in Public were engaged by the ARDC to promote the upcoming article in <i>New Phytologist</i> which explores, in part, how the integration of regional database like AusTraits doubled trait coverage for the Australian flora.	
Presentation at ALA all-staff meeting, May 2023	Project Manager Lizzy Wenk was invited to present to the entire staff at ALA, "Intro to AusTraits"	
Seminar, Evolution and Ecology Research Centre, UNSW	Falster DS "The eco-evolutionary forces shaping the large-scale structure of Australian vegetation"	
Conference presentation, Ecological Society of Australia, November 2022	Wenk et al "The AusTraits database structure and R package: introducing a tool for building ecological trait databases", Ecological Society of Australia, 1 December 2022	
Conference presentation, Ecological Society of Australia, November 2022	Falster et al "How adaptation could reshape forest structure and traits in +3deg world vegetation", Ecological Society of Australia, 1 December 2022	
Conference presentation, Ecological Society of Australia, November 2022	Coleman et al "Rough or smooth - building a consistent dataset of eucalypt bark traits", Ecological Society of Australia, 1 December 2022	
Conference presentation, ARDC Vocabulary Symposium, November 2022	Wenk et al "Documenting the AusTraits ontology", ARDC Vocabulary Symposium, 15 November 2022	https://zenodo.org/record/7834738#.ZGNT6M5Bwj4
Conference presentation, Open Traits Network,	Wenk et al "The AusTraits data structure and R package: introducing a	

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
September 2022	tool for building ecological trait databases”, Open Traits Network, 1 September 2022	
Conference presentation, Ecological Society of Australia, November 2021	Gallagher et al “Plant trait composition at the continental scale: using AusTraits to map trait variation and functional diversity across Australia”, Ecological Society of Australia, 23 November 2021	
Conference presentation, Ecological Society of Australia, November 2021	Wenk et al “Introduction to AusTraits”, Ecological Society of Australia, 23 November 2021	
Conference presentation, Genomics for Australian Plants, November 2021	Wenk et al “An introduction to AusTraits”; Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP) phylogenomics mini symposium, 16 November 2021.	
Working group presentation, DiveRS working group, November 2021	Sauquet et al “AusTraits: a national database on the traits of Australia’s complete flora”, DiveRS working group (Montpellier, France), November 25 2021	
Conference presentation, Australasian Systematic Botany Society, July 2021	Sauquet et al “AusTraits: a national database on the traits of Australia’s complete flora”, Australasian Systematic Botany Society Annual Conference, 12-16 July 2021	
Conference presentation, Australasian Systematic Botany Society Student and Early-Career Researcher Conference, November 2022	Coleman D, Falster D, Wenk E, Sauquet H. Nov. 2022. Generating trait databases from flora descriptions. Australasian Systematic Botany Society Student and Early-Career Researcher Conference (14-17 Nov. 2022; Mt Annan, Australia).	
Conference presentation, Australasian Systematic Botany Society Student and Early-Career Researcher Conference,	Dun L, Falster D, Wenk E, Barrett R, Gallagher R, Sauquet H. Nov. 2022. Building a dataset of floral traits for the Australian flora. Australasian Systematic Botany Society Student and	

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
November 2022	Early-Career Researcher Conference (14-17 Nov. 2022; Mt Annan, Australia).	

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	Automated methods that allow automated counting of downloads from Zenodo, citations of paper and data releases, and API hits. These are intermittently updated on our website at https://austraits.org/impact/
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	We received advice from users throughout the project period, taking onboard suggestions and making adjustments to our workflow. In particular, we completely revamped how “context properties” are mapped into AusTraits, following suggestion from research in multiple disciplines that ecological data are often meaningless if detailed contexts are not documents. The ability to map context properties is still lacking from other global databases and database structures standards.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	We are partaking in the ARDC NDA Impact Reporting Workshop
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	The core AusTraits team and the AusTraits advisory committee have discussed the monitoring framework we established and agree this suffices.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

The AusTraits project began as an endeavour to build a large, harmonised open-source database of Australian plant trait data, merging in data from disparate sources. All workflows were coded in R and all code was open source, freely available on the project’s GitHub repository. We quickly discovered that researchers were not just interested in using data from AusTraits to address research questions, but also

in reusing our workflows. This led to us formalising and generalising components of our workflow, and simply sharing our code with others. We now have groups using our taxon-matching algorithms to align outdated taxon names with the currently accepted names, which then allows them to link with AusTraits and other resources. We have groups using our core database-building workflow to build their own database, such as the ARDC-funded Invertebrates Australia group. And we have research groups worldwide embracing our efforts to align trait names and trait definitions across databases for greater interoperability. We knew that the skills we built learning how to interpret and synthesise data from disparate datasets into a single database would increase our future capabilities building trait databases, but we had not envisioned that we would also be building a broad toolset for the ecological trait community and are excited to see these tools being broadly reused. Finally, we attribute our success to the collegial, innovative core AusTraits team. We all worked very well together, each leading different work packages, setting achievable goals, regularly checking in with each other, and being respectful of each other's ideas. We set aside a day multiple times a year to have group workshops where we shared problems and brainstormed solutions across a range of topics, drawing upon the groups' diverse expertise.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

While we are overall satisfied with our work toward developing AusTraits into a National Data Asset, there are a few work packages that remain incomplete and others whose proposed output shifted over the duration of the funding.

In general, the reason that a small number of work packages remain incomplete or were modified was because of the changing time commitments of our partners. The potential for work partners priorities to shift was anticipated in our original project plan and contingencies identified. Many of the work packages required a very specific technical or domain skillset, such that an alternative person could not rapidly take over the work. For instance, we nominated four data portals that would partner with AusTraits to display AusTraits data, but for three of these, other commitments have forced them to delay integration with AusTraits.

Within the core AusTraits team, we struggled to find a team member with coding skills to enhance the AusTraits workflow, eventually requiring other team members to do more coding than anticipated or learn new skills; we've successfully completed this work package but not as efficiently as hoped.

The development of a Minimum Trait Set (MTS) and the integration of MTS data into AusTraits was not completed as envisioned. The project partner who was to lead this work package moved to a higher-level role with demanding new responsibilities half-way through the project and was unable to complete development of the MTS. We reimaged our work package and redeployed these resources to focus on

trait data extraction from published national and state floras, which added more than 570,000 new trait observations to the database (far more than would have come via completing the MTS). There is significant overlap in the traits captured in taxonomic descriptions and those that will ultimately comprise the MTS, and the traits added from this data scraping endeavour both add significant data coverage to AusTraits and will facilitate the development of an MTS in the future.

One of the most unexpectedly difficult components of the project had been “publishing vocabularies”. From the beginning we fully embraced establishing both our database structure and our trait dictionary as published vocabularies, but we did not accurately estimate the time required to complete this work. We had imagined there would exist a protocol or template to assist in publishing vocabularies, but instead discovered it was a project we had to begin from scratch. We are continually grateful for the mentoring we’ve received from ARDC staff, yet still found ourselves struggling with both conceptual and technical roadblocks. We’ve worked through them one by one and now have a formally published trait dictionary and a draft ontology for our database structure, but repeatedly wished there had been a clearer path forward. It has become clear to us why most efforts by ecologists to create a formal vocabulary end without a vocabulary being published, while the efforts of bioinformaticians to build formal database structures are not adopted by ecologists!